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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad

Chairman, Editorial Board

Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities

Gamji Institute for Training and Research

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF APPRAISAL FAIRNESS IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SUBJECTIVE APPRAISALS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF THE BAUCHI STATE TEACHERS SERVICE COMMISSION

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ABSTRACT

Insufficient attention has been given to understanding how fairness of appraisals influences the relationship between subjective assessments and overall employee performance evaluations. Despite its complex nature, encompassing elements like transparency, equity, and procedural justice, the impact of appraisal fairness on how subjective assessments are interpreted and accepted remains unclear. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating how the fairness of appraisals mediates the relationship between subjective assessments and employee performance appraisal, specifically within the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC). Using a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional survey design, the study surveyed 5,016 individuals, selecting 355 respondents through cluster sampling. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale. Structural equation modeling conducted with Smart PLS-SEM version 4, revealed a significant positive relationship between the variables under investigation. The study was grounded in Equity and Organizational Justice Theories. The findings indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between subjective appraisal and employee performance evaluations, with appraisal fairness playing a substantial mediating role. This novel perspective contributed to discussions on human resource development practices, offering insights valuable to both academics and practitioners. The practical implications signified the importance of fair and transparent appraisal systems, while the theoretical implications highlight the significance of fairness perceptions in equity and organizational justice theories. Recommendations from the study include continuous enhancement of appraisal systems and the need for ongoing research and collaborative efforts to introduce innovative approaches ensuring fairness in performance evaluations within the Bauchi State TSC.

Keywords: Employee Performance Appraisal, Subjective Appraisal, Appraisal Fairness, Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission, Bauchi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance appraisal is a cornerstone in human resource management practices, serving as a crucial tool for evaluating employees, providing feedback, and influencing decisions related to promotions, compensation, and training (Rodrigues, Gomes, and Junça 2023). Organizations are recognizing the limitations of traditional, top-down approaches and the need for more dynamic and equitable performance assessment methods (Khan, 2019). The complexity of employee performance involves its impact on fairness, recognition, rewards, and the challenges in conducting fair and effective performance appraisals (Pahos & Galanaki, 2020; Kim & Rubianty, 2019). The effectiveness of performance appraisals is crucial for human capital development, organizational success, and improving employee performance (Abdulkhaliq & Mohammadali, 2019; Abbas, 2019; Brutus & Baronian, 2020). Stakeholders consider appraisals effective when perceived as valuable, emphasizing their role in determining organizational outcomes (Giles & Mossholder, 1990; Levy & Williams, 2018; Murphy, 2020).

The study zooms in on the significance relationships between subjective appraisal, appraisal fairness, and their combined impact on employee performance. Subjective appraisal, influenced by individual biases, introduces complexity, impacting how employees perceive fairness in the appraisal process. The study explores the mediating role of appraisal fairness in shaping the outcomes of subjective appraisals on employee performance. Understanding these dynamics is crucial as organizations strive for effective, equitable, and transparent performance appraisal systems. Despite the significance of performance appraisal, there's a notable gap in understanding the mediating role of appraisal fairness between subjective appraisal and employee performance outcomes. Fairness in appraisal process significantly influences employees' perceptions of legitimacy, equity, and credibility regarding the outcomes (Rodrigues, Gomes, and Junça 2023). This research aims to address these gaps, contributing to the discourse on best practices in performance appraisal and assisting organizations in navigating the complexities of the modern organizational landscape. Additionally, the study addresses claims of insufficient mechanisms for appraising exceptional employees within the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC), building upon previous research highlighting the need to examine and improve appraisal practices in public

organizations and educational institutions (Atakpa, Ocheni & Nwankwo, 2021; Iorfa, 2021; Adebayo, 2020).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The current literature on employee performance appraisal in educational institutions (Azib, 2020; Cardy, 2019; Memon, 2019; Rodrigues, Gomes & Junça, 2023; Charles, 2022; Olubukola & Pauline, 2022; Atakpa, Ocheni & Nwankwo, 2021; Iorfa, 2021; Adebayo, 2020) confirmed its crucial role in enhancing workforce productivity, professional development, and organizational effectiveness. However, in the context of the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission, there is a notable research gap concerning the influence of subjective appraisal practices on the overall performance appraisal process. Lack of exploration in this area hinders the development of targeted strategies to optimize the performance evaluation system. Additionally, while subjective appraisal practices are recognized as influential (Norfarizal, 2019), the potential mediating role of appraisal fairness in shaping the relationship between subjective appraisal and the overall employee performance appraisal process has received insufficient attention. Despite being a multifaceted concept involving transparency, equity, and procedural justice, the impact of appraisal fairness on the interpretation and acceptance of subjective appraisal outcomes remains unclear. Similarly, the scarcity of empirical investigations into the mediating effects of appraisal fairness (Zahida, 2022; Olubukola & Pauline, 2022) represents a substantial void in understanding the intricate dynamics involved in employee performance appraisal within the educational sector. While extensive literature explores various aspects of performance appraisal, the specific mediating role of appraisal fairness between the relationship of subjective appraisal and employee performance has received limited attention.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to examine the mediating effect of appraisal fairness between the relationship of subjective appraisal and employee performance appraisal among staff of Bauchi state Teachers Service Commission. To achieve the targeted goal, survey was carried out among 355 employees within the commission from the three geographical zones in Bauchi State. Hence, the specific objectives are outline below:

- i. To examine the relationship between subjective appraisal and appraisal fairness at Bauchi Sate Teachers Service Commission.

- ii. To assess the relationship between appraisal fairness and employee performance appraisal at Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission
- iii. To evaluate the relationship between subjective appraisal and employee performance appraisal at Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission
- iv. To investigate the mediating relationship between subjective appraisal, appraisal fairness, and employee performance appraisal at Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study holds and contributed significantly on various fronts. Primarily, it offers practical insights crucial for organizations, especially in the public sector, exemplified by the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of the significance relationship among subjective appraisal, appraisal fairness, and employee performance is indispensable for these organizations. It enables them to fine-tune and optimize their performance appraisal systems, thereby fostering enhanced organizational efficiency. Additionally, the study's findings can actively contribute to shaping policies and guidelines governing employee performance appraisal in educational institutions. This contribution is significant in cultivating an atmosphere characterized by fairness and transparency. Lastly, the research, by illuminating the mediating role of appraisal fairness, provides valuable insights into the mechanisms fostering fair and constructive performance appraisals. These insights, in turn, have the potential to significantly boost organizational effectiveness. The study emerges as a valuable resource with relevance for practitioners, policymakers, and scholars alike.

Similarly, by focusing on Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission, this study specifically analyzes how appraisal fairness impacts teacher evaluation and performance appraisal within the commission. The choice to focus on the Commission for this research study may have been influenced by the organization as a governmental entity responsible for overseeing teachers and educational policies, the fairness and efficiency of its appraisal processes therefore, are crucial for improving educational outcomes. The ultimate goal is to propose effective solutions to the challenges facing the employee performance appraisal system in this particular case study. The researchers conducted a cross-sectional survey using a quantitative approach to investigate the relationships among the study's variables. The sample size was determined using Toro Yamane formula

to represent a subset of the total population being studied. Data analysis was performed using Smart PLS-SEM version 4 for the procedures, while SPSS version 23 was used for data screening exercise.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review chapter provides a comprehensive exploration into the mediation of appraisal fairness between the relationship of subjective appraisal and employee performance evaluations within Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC). Initially, the chapter delves into a conceptual review, and subsequently, the theoretical and empirical review to examine the existing theories, models, and empirical studies related to appraisal fairness, subjective appraisal, and their influence on employee performance appraisal outcomes. Incorporating insights from prior research, the research framework was established, outlining the hypothesized relationships and the proposed mediation of appraisal fairness.

2.1 EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL

Employee performance appraisal is a crucial element in human resource management, playing indispensable role in evaluating an employee's work-related accomplishments, skills, strengths, weaknesses, and overall contributions to an organization (Murphy, 2020; Babagana, 2018). The literature aims to explore the multifaceted purposes, diverse methods, challenges, and evolving landscape of performance management in employee performance appraisal practice. The multidimensional purpose of employee performance appraisal is highlighted by its role in providing feedback to employees. This process facilitates communication between supervisors and employees, supporting a comprehensive understanding of individual performance. Feedback serves as a foundation for identifying areas of improvement, setting goals, and supporting career growth. Additionally, performance appraisal is crucial in making decisions related to compensation, promotions, and terminations, aligning individual performance with organizational objectives and strategic goals (Armstrong, 2020). Various methods are employed in employee performance appraisal, such as graphic rating scales, 360-degree feedback, and behaviorally anchored rating scales (Armstrong, 2020). The choice of method depends on organizational preferences, job roles, and desired outcomes. While enhancing the process's effectiveness, these methods pose challenges, including biases in

subjective evaluations, inconsistent assessments due to lack of rater training, and potential communication issues affecting fairness and transparency. Effective communication of appraisal results is crucial for maximizing benefits.

Similarly, clear communication aids in understanding performance expectations, fosters employee development, and establishes a connection between individual performance and organizational objectives. This transparency contributes to a positive organizational culture and employee engagement. The contemporary landscape has shifted towards continuous performance management, emphasizing regular feedback, ongoing goal-setting, and continuous skill enhancement. Organizations are moving away from traditional annual performance reviews to a more dynamic and agile approach that aligns with today's fast-paced business environment. Legal and ethical considerations are paramount, requiring adherence to principles of fairness, confidentiality, and transparency to maintain the integrity of the process. Ensuring fair and unbiased appraisals contributes to employee trust and organizational credibility. In conclusion, employee performance appraisal remains a standard and essential practice in organizations. When adequately managed, it serves as a powerful tool for holding all employees accountable. By understanding the fundamental aspects, challenges, and evolving trends in performance appraisal, organizations can implement fair, accurate, and beneficial systems for both employees and the organization (Khan, 2019).

2.2 APPRAISAL FAIRNESS

Appraisal fairness significantly impacts the effectiveness of employee performance appraisal systems. It has been reiterated that employees find an appraisal system satisfactory only when it is perceived as fair and equitable (Nutakor, 2019). Fairness in appraisals is crucial for building trust and confidence among employees in the evaluation process. When the system is perceived as fair, transparent, and unbiased, it enhances trust in individual performance evaluation, fostering a positive employer-employee relationship and a motivating work environment. Fair appraisal systems motivate employees to invest effort in improving performance, anticipating fair recognition and rewards. This positive feedback loop encourages skill enhancement and contributions to organizational goals. Job satisfaction is positively influenced by fair appraisal practices, as they recognize employees' contributions, fostering a sense of value and commitment.

This correlation contributes to lower turnover rates and reduced absenteeism, promoting employee retention and organizational cost reduction (Rodrigues, Gomes & Junça, 2023). Moreover, fairness in appraisals nurtures a sense of organizational justice, foundational for creating a positive work culture where employees feel respected and valued. Fair appraisals contribute to the overall perception of organizational justice, reinforcing the idea that employees are evaluated based on merit and in alignment with organizational values. Beyond motivation and satisfaction, fair appraisals facilitate employee development through constructive feedback and engagement. Constructive feedback aids professional growth, allowing employees to identify improvement areas and align their skills with organizational objectives. Fair appraisals encourage open communication between employees and supervisors, fostering an environment of continuous improvement and learning. Importantly, fair appraisals ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards, signaling the organization's commitment to upholding ethical principles and complying with regulations. This commitment enhances the organization's reputation and reinforces its dedication to treating employees with integrity and fairness. Fair appraisal system is crucial for cultivating trust, motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational justice, creating a positive work environment conducive to improved performance, employee growth, and overall organizational success. Organizations prioritizing and implementing fair appraisal practices benefit from enhanced employee engagement, satisfaction, and retention, contributing to a positive organizational culture and long-term success (Olubukola & Pauline, 2022).

2.2 SUBJECTIVE APPRAISAL

Subjective appraisal, an evaluation method based on supervisors' judgments rather than solely measurable metrics, adds a personalized dimension to the assessment process. One key advantage lies in providing personalized feedback, considering qualitative aspects like behavior and attitude, leading to a holistic understanding of an employee's performance (Cardy, 2019). This feedback helps employees identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for growth, contributing to professional development. Subjective appraisal is motivating when employees feel understood and appreciated for their unique contributions, fostering connection and engagement. Acknowledging individual efforts serves as a powerful motivator, encouraging positive contributions to organizational goals. However, subjectivity introduces challenges related to biases, such as novelty, halo, and leniency

effects (Norfarizal, 2019). Organizations must manage biases effectively for fairness and accuracy. Striking a balance between subjectivity and objectivity, aligning evaluations with goals, and fostering strong supervisor-employee relationships are crucial. Training programs on evaluation techniques, bias reduction, and communication skills contribute to fair assessments and supervisor professional development. An integrative approach combining subjective appraisals with quantitative metrics in performance management systems offers a comprehensive view of employee performance. This balanced model leverages both measures for a holistic understanding, contributing to a culture of continuous improvement, employee engagement, and professional development (Sofia, 2021).

2.3 THEORETICAL REVIEW

The research study relied on Equity Theory as the main, supported by Organizational Justice Theory, to gain insights into and enhance employee performance appraisal practices in the selected case study. John Stacey Adams introduced the Equity theory in 1963, emphasizing how employees perceive fairness in work inputs and outcomes. Applied to employee performance appraisals, the theory stresses the need for a balance between an employee's contributions and the rewards or compensation they receive. Higher pay and rewards generally motivate employees to sustain high performance (Locke, 2019). Adams highlighted the link between fairness perceptions and worker motivation, emphasizing the value of fair treatment in workplaces. Equity Theory holds significant implications for the current study in employee performance appraisals, emphasizing the importance of balancing the evaluation of an employee's contributions and associated rewards. This theory also assists the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC) in preventing underpayment or overpayment by remaining attentive to perceptions of inequity, conducting regular appraisals, and ensuring fairness in distributing sacrifices within the commission.

Organizational Justice Theory, introduced by Thibaut and Walker in the mid-1970s, focuses on ensuring procedural fairness in resolving disputes related to employee performance appraisal. Linked to employee performance appraisal by Greenberg in 1986, this theory emphasizes an organization's commitment to fairness in its practices. Organizational justice originates from decisions made during the appraisal process (Tang, Sarsfield, & Baldwin, 1996). Employee performance appraisal significantly influences

organizational outcomes, and when perceived as biased, appraisals can lead to dissatisfaction (Ilgen, 1979; Rietsche, 2021; Gruman & Saks, 2019). In essence, equity and organizational justice are foundational principles supporting the importance of fairness in appraisals. These principles impact employee satisfaction and performance within the appraisal system of the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission.

2.5 APPRAISAL FAIRNESS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL

Zahida (2022) delved into the realm of performance appraisal fairness and its impact on employee performance within the higher education sector. The research emphasized the significance of academicians' satisfaction with performance appraisal, emphasizing key factors such as procedural fairness, the outcomes received, and the clarity of information regarding system procedures. The findings highlighted the critical role of employee acceptance of the appraisal system in terms of fairness and satisfaction. The study posited that when employees perceive the appraisal system as fair and satisfactory, it contributes to organizational success by elevating performance levels. This aligns with the findings of Olubukola and Pauline (2022), who conducted a study on Performance Appraisal Fairness and Employees' Performance specifically within the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA). The results of this study revealed a robust positive relationship between appraisal fairness and employees' performance appraisal. The implications drawn from these studies underline the importance of ensuring distributive, procedural, and interactional fairness in the appraisal rating assessment process.

In light of these findings, organizations, particularly those in the higher education sector and entities like the NTA, are encouraged to prioritize and enhance the fairness dimensions of their performance appraisal systems. This involves not only the fair distribution of rewards but also transparent and just procedures, as well as respectful and clear communication throughout the appraisal process. The findings of these studies collectively underscore the importance of fair and transparent performance appraisal systems in fostering employee satisfaction and, consequently, organizational success. Ensuring fairness in the appraisal process is not only a means to acknowledge and motivate employees but also a strategic imperative for organizations aiming to optimize performance and achieve sustainable growth. The first hypotheses stated that:

There is significance relationship between appraisal fairness and employee performance appraisal in Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC).

2.5 SUBJECTIVE APPRAISAL AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL

In a research study conducted by Janvinen, (2022), the focus was on gaining a nicety understanding of subjectivity in employee performance appraisal and its implications for procedural justice across diverse contexts. This investigation involved surveying 160 middle managers in Vietnam, revealing substantial impacts of subjective appraisal practices among this managerial cohort. To enhance fairness in subjective appraisal, the study proposed the implementation of a formal performance appraisal design, aiming to achieve precision and consistency in the assessments of individuals under evaluation. The study by Janvinen (2022) contributes to the existing body of research by shedding light on the multifaceted nature of subjectivity in employee performance appraisal. While numerous studies address subjectivity in a broad sense, acknowledging various aspects of supervisor discretion, others take a more specific focus on distinct elements.

Bellavance, (2020) delved into the use of subjective performance appraisal and ex-post flexibility concerning the weighting of multiple measures, while Bol (2021) concentrates on ex-post discretionary adjustments in response to uncontrollable events. Bicudo de Castro (2019) introduces two concepts of subjectivity: rule-driven and supervisor-driven subjective appraisal. Additionally, Ugoani (2020) emphasizes the significance of addressing performance appraisal issues, particularly in charitable organizations. Despite the growing empirical research on the subjective appraisal process, scholars recognize limitations in the literature concerning subjective appraisal and its measurement constructs. Considering that various facets of subjective appraisal serve different purposes and may impact organizational outcomes diversely, there is a recognized need to comprehensively capture the notion of subjectivity in employee performance appraisal. Therefore, the second hypothesis underlines:

There is significant relationship between subjective appraisal and employee performance appraisal at Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission.

2.6 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The research framework was developed to address gaps identified in existing literature on employee performance appraisal. Through a meticulous process involving the analysis of empirical studies, potential relationships among research constructs were identified. The framework's foundation was laid using evidence from prior literature. However, the

literature review highlighted the need for additional studies to explore connections between variables in practical and contextual settings, as suggested by Tanya (2019), Ugoani (2020), Zahida (2022), Malumba (2021), and Rodrigues (2023). The visually presented research framework illustrates potential mediating effects or relationships, depicting the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable based on insights from scrutinized literature

Figure: 2.1 A research framework with a mediating relationship between dependent and independent variables

The decision to incorporate the mediator into the framework was based on the principles and theories outlined by Baron and Kenny (1986). As per Baron and Kenny's (1986) framework, the independent variable X is hypothesized to influence the outcome variable Y by one or more intervening variables M, termed as the mediator in this specific framework (X, M, Y). Baron and Kenny (1986) further assert that a mediator represents a causal sequence wherein the impact of one or more independent variables is transmitted to the dependent variable through the third variable.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research study utilized a quantitative research approach adopting cross-sectional survey research design to collect data from the respondents at a single point of time. The target population encompasses the academic staff working in Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC). Based on the statistical data obtained from the Ministry of Education Bauchi State, the population was determined to be 5,016 academic staff members. A sample size of 371 participants were selected, and ultimately, 335 valid responses were used for the analyses. The study employed a probability cluster sampling technique to select participants from the target population. To ensure the validity of the

research instrument, guaranteeing its ability to accurately capture the intended data, the content underwent validation by a research expert. The scale items were developed from previous research studies (Thuy & Janne 2022; Norfarizal, 2019; Al-bhaidani, 2022; Olubukola & Pauline 2022; Zahida, 2022) and modified to be more contextually relevant. Additionally, the collected data were analyzed using Smart PLS Version 4 software. PLS Predict was utilized to assess the predictive power of the model, employing techniques such as Cross Validation Predictive Assessment Test (CVPAT). Additionally, Important Performance Map Analysis (IPMA) was applied to evaluate the importance and performance of each of the research construct (Hair, Sarstedt, Pick, Liengard, Radomir, Ringle, 2022).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

The survey questionnaires, totaling three hundred and seventy-one (371), were distributed to the participants and three hundred and thirty-five (335) were successfully retrieved, yielding a commendable response rate of 90.32%. Unfortunately, thirty (30) questionnaires, accounting for 8.08%, were not recovered due to various reasons. Six (6) questionnaires, representing 1.6%, were rendered unusable as they contained missing values and lacked essential information. The demographic data of the responded revealed that majority of the respondents were male (89.9%), and most fell within the 30-39 age brackets (93.1%). The largest portions of the respondents were married (88.1%), and a significant number were graduates (78.8%). Out of 335 respondents, 171 (51%) were staff members with the highest level of work experience in the chosen case study. The subsequent analysis was conducted based on the collected questionnaires. The data gathered for the research study underwent analysis using second-generation multivariate data analysis software, specifically Smart PLS version 4. Furthermore, data screening exercise was carried out to purify the collected data using SPSS version 23.

4.1 MEASUREMENT MODEL (OUTER MODEL)

Wong, (2019) asserted that, measurement model evaluates the quality criteria of the research constructs and before delving into the assessment of path coefficients within the structural model, as recommended, the research study evaluates the indicator reliability (Outer loadings), internal consistency reliability (Composite reliability), convergent validity, and discriminant validity of the reflective measurement model. This confirmation is essential to ensure that these components meet satisfactory standards,

Table 4.1
Measurement Model Path Coefficient

Constructs	Indicators	Loadings	Composite Cronbach		AVE
Performance Appraisal	PA1	0.864	0.900	0.899	0.656
	PA2	0.831			
	PA3	0.775			
	PA4	0.797			
	PA5	0.815			
	PA6	0.699			
	PA7	0.735			
Appraisal Fairness	AF1	0.739	0.916	0.906	0.683
	AF2	0.824			
	AF3	0.916			
	AF4	deleted			
	AF5	0.797			
	AF6	0.851			
	AF7	0.820			
Subjective Appraisal	SA1	0.796	0.907	0.903	0.675
	SA2	0.845			
	SA3	0.868			
	SA4	deleted			
	SA5	0.874			
	SA6	0.745			
	SA7	0.785			

The table presented above illustrated the reliability analysis of outer loadings and employee performance appraisal, exhibited a composite reliability of 0.900, accompanied by an average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.656. Additionally, the mediator, appraisal fairness, displayed a composite reliability of 0.916, along with an average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.683. Moreover, the results of the outer loadings reliability analysis indicated that subjective appraisal demonstrated a composite reliability of 0.907, with an

average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.673. According to Bagozzi & Yi, (1988; Wong, 2019; Hair, *et al.*, 2022), the minimum acceptable AVE should be 0.5 and above meaning an AVE of 0.5 or higher signified that the construct predicts or explains 50% or more of the variance in the indicators. Two indicators AF4 (0.296), SA4 (0.253) were eliminated as their outer loadings fell below the prescribed threshold of 0.7, as suggested by Hair, *et al.*, (2022).

Table 4.2 Path Coefficient (Hypotheses Testing) Total Effect

R/Ship Level	Beta Decision	STDEV	T-Value	P-Value		Confidence
				Lower	Upper	
SA ->AF	0.163	0.034	4.741	0.000	0.096	0.230
Supported						
AF -> PA	0.383	0.065	5.941	0.000	0.256	0.510
Supported						
SA-> PA	0.346	0.056	6.193	0.000	0.237	0.455
Supported						
SA ->AF->PA	0.163	0.034	4.741	0.000	0.096	0.230
Supported						

R² 0.810: Level of significance: **p<0.05 Source: Field Work 2023 Smart PLS4 PA: Performance Appraisal, AF: Appraisal Fairness, SA: Subjective Appraisal

The relationship between subjective appraisal (SA) and employee performance appraisal (PA) was determined to be significant ($\beta=0.034$, $T=4.741$, $p=0.000<0.05$) with a T-value greater than the critical value of 1.96 (two-tailed) at 95% confidence interval, the research hypothesis was confirmed. This outcome further supported the findings of Rodrigues, Gomes & Junca, (2023), demonstrating a positive and significant relationship between satisfaction with appraisals and employee performance appraisal. Moreover, it revealed that employees in the private sector exhibit higher satisfaction levels with their performance appraisals compared to those in the public sector.

The second alternate hypothesis depicting a relationship between appraisal fairness (AF) and employee performance appraisal (PA) was significance and supported by a T-value of

5.941 and a P-value of 0.000. With the T-value surpassing the significance threshold of 1.96 at 95% confidence level (two-tailed), the alternate hypothesis was confirmed. The results correspond with Zahida's (2022) investigation into the impact of appraisal fairness on employee performance appraisal within higher education. The researcher indicated that academician satisfaction with performance appraisals was strongly associated with both procedural aspects and the resulting outcomes. Additionally, the study by Olubukola & Pauline, (2022) resonates with these findings, revealing a robust positive correlation between appraisal fairness and employee performance appraisal. The study recommended that NTA (Nigerian Television Authority) should maintain fair assessment practices in appraisals to enhance and ensure consistent improvements in performance appraisal procedures.

The third hypothesis suggesting a significant relationship between subjective appraisal (SA) and employee performance appraisal (PA) was supported. This significance relationship was verified by the analysis yielding a T-value of 6.193 above the critical value of 1.96 at 95% confidence level, and a corresponding P-value of 0.000 falling below the statistical threshold 0.005. With T-value surpassing the specified significance threshold of 1.96 at 95% confidence level, signified that subjective appraisal significantly influences employee performance appraisal within the chosen case study.

4.2 RESULT OF THE MEDIATION ANALYSIS

Hair *et al.*, (2022) emphasized that assessing the strength of the relationship (mediation) is best achieved through the utilization of total effect and variance account for (VAF). VAF serves as a statistical ratio of the beta coefficient as suggested (Hair *et al.*, 2019). To calculate variance account for, $VAF = \text{Indirect} / \text{Total effect}$. In accordance with this, VAF values below the 0.2 threshold indicate the absence of mediation in the model, values between 0.2 and 0.8 suggest partial mediation, and a VAF exceeding 0.8 indicates full mediation (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Table 4.3

Mediation Analysis (H6: SA ->AF->PA)

Type of Effect	Effect	Beta	T-Value
Decision			
Total Effect	SA -> PA	0.275	4.323
			Sig Total Effect

Indirect Effect	SA ->AF->PA	0.163	4.741	Sig Indirect Effect
	VAF		IE/TE	59%
Conclusion	Moderately Partial Mediation Exists			

SA: Subjective Appraisal, PA: Employee Performance Appraisal, AF: Appraisal Fairness, VAF: Variance Account For. IE: Indirect Effect, TE: Total Effect

The results of the mediation analysis as presented in Table 4.3, revealed significance in the total effect of the relationship between subjective appraisal (SA) and employee performance appraisal (PA) ($\beta=0.275$, $T\text{-value}=4.323>1.96$), in comparison to the indirect effect ($\beta=0.163$, $T\text{-value}=4.741>1.96$). Furthermore, the variance accounted for (VAF) demonstrated a value of 59%, indicating a moderately substantial level of partial mediation among the constructs within the model. These findings are consistent with observations made by scholars in the field (Hair *et al.*, 2022).

4.3 ASSESSMENT OF COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION AND EFFECT SIZE

Coefficients of determination demonstrate how much the exogenous constructs collectively contributed to the model's ability to explain variances in the endogenous construct (Wong, 2019). Following the thresholds proposed by Hair *et al.*, (2022) of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.7 for weak, moderate, and strong coefficients of determination, the overall coefficient of determination for the endogenous construct (0.810) was considered strong. This implies that the constructs explained 81% variance in the endogenous construct. Similarly, the study examined the effect of exogenous variables on the endogenous construct using f statistic. Following Cohen's (1988) guidelines, f^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effect sizes, respectively.

Table 4.4

Coefficient of determination and Effect Size

	R^2	f^2
PA	0.801	
AF	0.851	0.355
SA		0.365

The robust coefficient of determination identified for the endogenous as well as the mediator indicated that the variables played a substantial role in the model, demonstrating a significant portion of the observed variance in the relationship between the constructs. Similarly, a sizable effect size implied the impact of appraisal fairness on subjective appraisal and, consequently, employee performance appraisal is considerable and influential. This noteworthy effect size indicated the crucial importance of maintaining fairness in appraisal procedures, as it significantly molds various facets of employee performance and satisfaction within the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission.

5.1 RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The research findings stand to offer practical insights that can directly benefit the operational framework within the Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission. These implications may encompass strategies and recommendations aiming at enhancing the fairness and transparency of the appraisal process. These could include the development and implementation of clear guidelines and training programs for supervisors to ensure unbiased, consistent, and ethical evaluations. Moreover, fostering an environment that prioritizes fair appraisal procedures could be crucial to enhance employee morale, performance, and overall satisfaction within the commission. On a theoretical level, the implications stemming from this research contribute to the field of organizational psychology and management theories. Validating the role of appraisal fairness as a mediator signified the importance of organizational justice theories in understanding the dynamics of employee performance appraisal. It offers a fresh perspective on the significance relationship between employee fairness in the appraisal process and their subsequent appraisal satisfaction.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The research study identified significant relationship between the research variables, highlighting the mediating role of appraisal fairness between subjective appraisal and employee performance appraisal exercise. The statistical significance demonstrated the crucial influence of appraisal fairness on the overall effectiveness of performance appraisal systems. The positive link between subjective appraisal and appraisal fairness indicated that fairness is shaped by the subjectivity inherent in appraisal exercise. This emphasizes the importance for organizations to adopt transparent and objective appraisal procedures to enhance appraisal fairness. Additionally, the mediating role of appraisal

fairness suggested that fairness acts as a bridge, influencing how subjective appraisal affects overall employee performance evaluation. Perceiving the appraisal process as fair positively contributed to appraisal outcomes, helping to mitigate potential biases associated with subjective judgments.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the conclusions, various suggestions and recommendations emerged:

1. **Enhance Transparency and Communication:** Organizations should focus on enhancing transparency in the appraisal process. Clear communication of evaluation criteria and performance expectations can contribute to a more objective and fair appraisal process. Regularly communicate the purpose and methodology of the appraisal to employees to minimize ambiguity.
2. **Implement Training Programs:** Provide training programs for supervisors and evaluators on objective performance appraisal techniques. Equipping them with the necessary skills to conduct fair and unbiased assessments can lead to more accurate and reliable performance exercise.
3. **Regularly Review and Update Appraisal Processes:** Regular reviews can identify potential biases and areas for improvement. By addressing subjective appraisal and emphasizing the mediating role of appraisal fairness, organizations can cultivate a performance appraisal environment that fosters employee satisfaction, engagement, and continuous improvement. Finally, the study findings are only limited to Academic staff of Bauchi State Teachers Service Commission (TSC) it is recommended that further research should incorporate both the management and the academic staff of the commission in their research sample.

Further studies should extend the research to encompass various cultural contexts within Nigeria or cross-national studies. Comparing how appraisal fairness operates in different cultural settings could highlight cultural influences on appraisal fairness and performance outcomes. Further research should also investigate additional variables or factors that might act as mediators or moderators within the relationship between appraisal fairness and employee performance like appraisal satisfaction and ethical behavior.

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